

23. Secrets and irreplicable reasons for the success of the US economic system and model based on historical, philosophical, and logical perspective

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Abstract

This article explores the U.S. economic system and model from multiple perspectives. Over the past century, the United States has achieved remarkable economic development, along with an appealing democratic model, advanced technology and education. However, when the U.S. spreads its models around the world, most recipient countries encounter failures like economic crises. The U.S. economic system is not a purely market - oriented system. It is a complex combination of politician or statesman behavior economy, political party behavior economy, political behavior economy, government behavior economy, market behavior economy, oligarchic behavior economy, military behavior economy, war behavior economy, and national behavior economy. There are numerous examples of this mixed - mode behavior. For example, the US has taken military orders from France in deals with Australia and Greece, disrupting normal diplomatic and procurement processes. In foreign trade, political factors have caused the United States to lose opportunities, such as in the case of the UAE's arms purchase. The U.S.-China trade friction since 2018 is detailed, with various tariff impositions, restrictions on Chinese companies like Huawei, and interference in investment and technology transfer. Similar frictions exist with other countries and regions, such as the EU, Japan, Mexico, and India. The United States also has a range of domestic economic policies, including tax cuts, stimulus bills, and infrastructure investment bills. The trade war has led to heavy losses for U.S. companies in market value, jobs, and increased household expenses. In addition, the Chip and Science Act shows government intervention. This complex model of economic behavior affects both the United States and the world. Other countries cannot replicate the U.S. model. The U.S. model is far from a free and democratic market economy as commonly believed. It has shown a complex behavioral economy dominated by politicians, government, and political parties, and economists should consider historical, philosophical, and logical aspects when analyzing it.

Keywords: market-oriented economy · politician or statesman behavior economy · political party behavior economy · political behavior economy · government behavior economy · market behavior economy · oligarchic behavior economy · military behavior economy · war behavior economy · national behavior economy · tariff rate · Free Trade Area (FTA) · globalization · chip · economic model · philosophical perspective · historical perspective

Over the past 100 years, the U.S. economy has made remarkable progress. Not only has GDP occupied the first place in the world for a long time, but the democratic political model of the United States has attracted the attention and appreciation of many people, and the science and technology and higher education of the United States have been upgraded to a new level unprecedented for mankind. A large number of talented people immigrated to the United States, bringing a constant stream of vitality to the country. In World War II, the sacrifice of American soldiers brought peace to the world, which is worthy of respect. Driven by politicians, management experts, economists, and the media, and various social groups, has led the public to habitually mistake the United States as a market-oriented economic nation.

However, as the United States continues to introduce its democratic, political and economic models to countries around the world, most of the recipient countries' practices have failed. Some countries have experienced serious economic crises, and some have fallen into the middle income trap. This prompted further research into the political and economic patterns of the United States. The author finds that the economic system of the United States is not a complete market economy system or a complete market-oriented economic system, but a highly centralized political party, politics, market, monopoly, war, military and state-owned behavioral economy system composed of two political parties, the government, and the backstage monopolistic consortium based on a historical, philosophical and practical point of view.

Almost every day, the economic behavior model of the United States can focus on showing the mixed pattern of politician or statesman behavior economy, political party behavior economy, political behavior economy, government behavior economy, market behavior economy, oligarchic behavior economy, military behavior economy, war behavior economy, and national behavior economy. The regional economy of the United States is the result of the integration of this comprehensive economic situation. This structure and trend not only brings about economic growth in the United States, but also brings about economic disasters or crises, which can be fully reflected in some major economic events. However, this economic model is almost impossible for other countries to replicate, and it is difficult for other developing countries to use the U.S. economic model to achieve truly prosperity. Once the U.S. economic model is introduced, it is likely to fall into the trap of long-term economic recession, or there will be huge fluctuations in the market economy or national economy. For example, we might examine the economic benefits achieved by the United States or the potential obstacles to economic development left behind by the frequent assertive actions taken by U.S. political parties or the government in recent years.

First, in September 2021, the United States snatched orders from France and signed a huge contract worth \$65.5 billion with Australia¹.

On September 16, 2021, French Foreign Minister Le Drion expressed his "extreme anger" to the French media, describing it as "C'est un coup dans le dos"².

On September 17, 2021, French Foreign Minister Le Delion announced in a press release that evening that, at the request of President Macron, France would immediately recall its two ambassadors to the United States and Australia to negotiate on Australia's unilateral tearing up of an agreement worth 56 billion euros with France

to build 12 submarines.

However, in 2008, then Prime Minister Kevin Rudd proposed a \$25 billion high-speed rail plan to improve people's livelihoods³, connecting Sydney and Melbourne, but it ultimately fell through. In recent years, in the crisis created by politicians, Australia has been the first to build nuclear submarines that cost more than high-speed rail.

Second, U.S. seizes order for French-contracted military helicopters⁴.

On December 10, 2022, the Australian military announced that it would forgo the purchase of helicopters from Europe and instead bring in Black Hawk and Sea Hawk helicopters from the United States. Australia will discontinue European helicopters and spend \$7 billion to buy 40 Lockheed Martin helicopters from the United States. However, the MRH-90 helicopter that Australia jettisoned was designed by the European company Airbus, in which France has a stake, which again amounts to the US taking business away from France to its detriment.

Third, on December 10, 2022, the United States announced military procurement cooperation with Greece⁴. The United States will provide Greece with four new frigates, and will also maintain and upgrade Greece's existing ships. The total price of this military procurement contract between the United States and Greece is about \$9.4 billion, of which \$6.9 billion is for the purchase of frigates, and the remaining \$2.5 billion is for the maintenance and upgrading of ships. Before negotiating with the United States, Greece had reached an agreement with France on military procurement cooperation. Although a military procurement contract had not yet been signed, a similar agreement worth €3 billion was originally scheduled to be finalized in December and officially signed. The French media believe that the United States has repeatedly disrupted France's military procurement orders, posing a significant threat to France. The actions of the United States not only violate international diplomatic rules, but also disrupt the normal military procurement process. Over time, not only France, but the whole world will be harmed.

Fourth, political factors have had a significant impact on the United States' foreign trade and have also led to the loss of trade opportunities for the United States. On December 3, 2022, the UAE signed a 17 billion euro (\$19.2 billion) military procurement contract with France⁴, including the purchase of 80 Rafale fighter jets and 12 Airbus Caracal military helicopters from France. On December 14, 2022, the Embassy of the United Arab Emirates in the United States stated that the country had suspended arms sales negotiations with the United Arab Emirates. In May 2019, during the President Trump era, the UAE decided to buy 50 F-35 fighter jets, 18 Reaper drones, and other weapons for \$23 billion. But during the President Biden era, the United States was filled with dirty water from the "Cold War mentality". As US media reported at the end of May 2021, the Biden administration imposed conditions on military sales, forcing the UAE to abandon the use of Huawei equipment and ordering the UAE to "keep a distance" from China and not allow the UAE to cooperate with China in building ports and other facilities. However, the UAE disagrees with the United States. After all, Huawei's equipment is not only good in performance, but also cost-effective.

Fifth, in March 2018, President Trump administration launched a trade war with

China based on the so-called "301 investigation"⁴, imposing high tariffs on about 360 billion US dollars of Chinese goods imported into the United States, and boasting that "trade wars are easy to fight and win". After President Biden administration took office in January 2021, it continued the previous administration's tariff policy toward China.

On August 31, 2019, CNBC (Consumer News and Business Channel) calculated an account for Trump President, stressing that "the trade war has already cost electronics companies to lose \$10 billion⁵, and the situation will be even worse from September 1." CNBC also said consumers' wallets in the U.S. will begin to be impacted.

According to relevant research, since the tariff came into effect, the trade war with China has cost U.S. companies to lose \$1.7 trillion in market value⁶, lost more than 24,000 jobs, and increased annual household expenses by nearly \$1,300. In the words of White House Press Secretary Jean Pierre, some of Trump's tariffs are "irresponsible" and do not advance the economic or national security of the United States, but instead increase household and business expenses. David Adelman, the former U.S. ambassador to Singapore, noted that "the trade war not only did not have a negative impact on the Chinese economy, but also, like a 'boomerang', harmed the U.S. economy in turn." So recently, over 6,000 companies in the United States have decided to jointly sue the U.S. government for the economic losses caused by this policy⁷.

However, we can be fully aware that the pattern of power of the political parties and the behind-the-scenes monopolistic consortia in the U.S. government can influence any major military expansion or world war in the world, provided they are truly willing and able to unleash good will.

Sixth, in August 2022, U.S. President Joe Biden signed the Chip and Science Act⁸, which authorizes nearly \$170 billion in funding for research and development projects across multiple federal agencies over the next five years. The bill aims to help the United States compete with China and provide \$52.7 billion in subsidies for semiconductor production and research in the United States, requiring any company receiving U.S. subsidies to manufacture chips locally in the United States.

Table 13. Evolutionary Record of U.S. Political Parties and Government Behavioral Economy in U.S.-China Trade Friction from August 2017 to January 2020⁹

NO.	Contents ⁹
1	In August 2017, President Trump of the United States instructed the Office of the United States Trade Representative (USTR) to conduct a 301 investigation into China. In March 2018, the USTR released its investigation findings, the 301 Report, accusing China of issues such as forced technology transfer and theft of US intellectual property rights. Based on this, Trump President imposed additional tariffs on China.
2	Starting June 11, 2018, the United States has tightened visa issuance for Chinese international students majoring in science, technology, engineering, mathematics, and other fields. This trend is gradually spreading and affecting the normal academic exchanges of other disciplines, and Chinese scholars studying in the United States have been unreasonably obstructed multiple times.

3	On June 15, 2018, the United States unilaterally tore up the consensus reached by both sides in May and proposed imposing 25% tariffs on \$50 billion worth of goods, to be implemented in two batches. On the same day, China decided to impose a 25% tariff on approximately \$50 billion worth of imported goods originating in the United States.
4	On June 18, 2018, Trump President instructed the U.S. Trade Representative to determine a list of \$200 billion worth of Chinese goods to be subject to additional tariffs, stating that if China takes retaliatory measures and refuses to change its "unfair" trade practices, an additional 10% tariff will be imposed. On June 27th, Trump announced that he would restrict China's investment in key technology industries in the United States.
5	On July 6, 2018, the United States implemented a 25% import tariff on \$34 billion worth of Chinese goods. On the same day, China imposed a 25% import tariff on U.S. products of the same size.
6	On August 1, 2018, President Trump threatened to increase the tariff rate on \$200 billion worth of goods to China from 10% to 25%. On August 3rd, China responded by imposing tariffs of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 25% on US\$60 billion worth of goods.
7	On August 8, 2018, the United States announced that it would impose tariffs on the remaining \$16 billion of imported goods worth \$50 billion from China on August 23. China announced on August 23rd that it would impose tariffs on \$16 billion worth of goods from the United States.
8	On September 18, 2018, the U.S. government officially announced a 10% tariff on about \$200 billion worth of products imported from China from September 24, and will increase the tariff rate to 25% from January 1, 2019. The United States also said that if China takes retaliatory measures against U.S. farmers or other industries, it will impose tariffs on approximately \$267 billion in Chinese products. The Chinese Ministry of Commerce responded on the same day that it would simultaneously counter the situation.
9	On October 1, 2018, negotiations on the U.S.-Canada Mexico Agreement were successful, with the establishment of a poison pill clause that stipulated that all three countries, the U.S.-Canada Mexico, were not allowed to sign agreements with "non-market economy" countries without authorization. This means that without the permission of the United States, the possibility of China signing free trade agreements with Canada and Mexico will become extremely slim; Even more serious is that if the United States includes this provision in its trade agreements with the European Union and Japan, negotiations on the China-Japan-South Korea Free Trade Area (FTA) and the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) will also be significantly affected.
10	On November 1, 2018, the U.S. Department of the Treasury's Foreign Investment Committee formally strengthened the review of foreign investment in core technology industries such as aerospace, biopharmaceuticals, and semiconductors, in accordance with the Foreign

	Investment Risk Review Modernization Act passed by the U.S. Congress in June, At the same time, the bill also requires the secretary of the U.S. Department of Commerce to submit reports to Congress every two years on "Chinese corporate entities' direct investment in the United States" and "investment by state-owned enterprises in the U.S. transportation industry".
11	On November 20, 2018, the U.S. Department of Commerce's Industrial Security Administration announced the proposed export control system for key technologies and related products and solicited public comments, and proposed to implement export controls on 14 core cutting-edge technologies, including biotechnology, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning.
12	On December 1, 2018, at the G20 Leaders' Summit in Buenos Aires, the heads of state of China and the United States reached a framework agreement for a temporary ceasefire and began 90 days of structural negotiations.
13	On January 30-31, 2019, the China -U.S. economic and trade negotiations made gradual progress. Both sides agreed to take effective measures to promote the balanced development of China-U.S. trade. China will vigorously expand imports of agricultural products, energy, industrial products, and service products from the United States. However, the two sides have not yet reached an agreement on structural issues such as the implementation of the agreement, intellectual property protection, and technology transfer. At the same time, the US continues to use special discriminatory measures to combat Huawei. On January 29, 2019, the U.S. Department of Justice announced 23 criminal lawsuits against Huawei and will request the extradition of Huawei's vice president and chief financial officer to Canada, escalating the global crackdown on Huawei.
14	On February 5, 2019, President Trump delivered his annual State of the Union speech to Congress, with the theme of "choosing greatness", reaffirming the principles of fair trade, defending American jobs, pursuing a foreign policy that puts American interests first, and using China as an economic and valuable adversary. On the same day, USTR released the 2018 "Report on China's Fulfillment of WTO Commitment", which pointed out that China still faces issues such as mandatory technology transfer, industrial policies, illegal export restrictions, and the electronic payment market not being opened to foreign investment. The Chinese Ministry of Commerce immediately objected.
15	On February 7, 2019, the White House released the Future Industrial Development Plan, proposing to focus on the four key technologies of artificial intelligence, advanced manufacturing, quantum information, and 5G technology to promote the prosperity of the U.S. economy and protect national security.
16	On February 14-15, 2019, the sixth round of China-US high-level economic and trade consultations concluded. The two sides discussed topics such as technology transfer, intellectual property protection, non-tariff barriers, service industries, agriculture, trade balance, and implementation mechanisms, and reached consensus on principles.

17	On February 21-24, 2019, the seventh round of the China-U.S. High-level Economic and Trade Consultation reached an important consensus. The two sides conducted negotiations on the text of the agreement, increased the content of the exchange rate and financial services negotiations, and made substantial progress.
18	On March 1, 2019, USTR announced that it would not increase the tariff rate on imported goods from China that had been subject to additional tariffs since September 2018, and would continue to maintain it at 10%. The Chinese side welcomes this.
19	On March 28-29, April 3-5, and April 30-May 1, 2019, the eighth, ninth, and tenth rounds of China-U.S. high-level economic and trade consultations continued to discuss relevant texts of the agreement, and continued to make progress.
20	On May 6, 2019, President Trump suddenly announced that starting May 10, he would impose tariffs on \$200 billion worth of imported goods that China had previously imposed 10% tariffs to 25%, and in the short term, he would impose tariffs on another \$325 billion worth of goods. On May 13, China announced an increase in tax rates to 10%, 20%, and 25% on \$60 billion worth of goods with 5% and 10% tariffs imposed by the United States starting June 1.
21	On May 15, 2019, U.S. President Trump signed an executive order declaring that the United States has entered a "national emergency" and that U.S. companies are not allowed to use telecommunications equipment produced by companies that pose a national security risk. The U.S. Department of Commerce's Bureau of Industry and Security listed Huawei as an export control "entity".
22	On June 29, 2019, at the G20 Leaders' Summit in Osaka, the heads of state of China and the United States agreed to promote a coordinated, cooperative and stable China-U.S. relationship and resume economic and trade negotiations on the basis of equality and mutual respect. The United States said it would no longer impose new tariffs on Chinese products during the negotiation period. The economic and trade teams of the two countries will discuss specific issues. President Trump announced that the U.S. company can continue to supply Huawei with components that do not involve national security.
23	On July 30-31, 2019, the U.S.-China economic and trade team held the twelfth round of economic and trade negotiations in Shanghai.
24	On August 2, 2019, US President Trump announced that the United States would impose a 10% tariff on \$300 billion worth of Chinese goods from September 1.
25	On August 6, 2019, the United States identified China as a "currency manipulator" and announced that it would approach the International Monetary Fund to eliminate the unfair competitive advantage brought about by China's actions. On August 9, 2019, the International Monetary Fund

	released China's annual Article IV consultation report, reiterating that "China's current account surplus declined in 2018, and the RMB exchange rate level was basically consistent with economic fundamentals", denying that China was a currency manipulator.
26	On August 15, 2019, the United States announced the imposition of a 10% tariff on Chinese goods worth \$300 billion in two batches, with implementation dates of September 1 and December 15, respectively.
27	On August 23, 2019, China announced tariffs of 5% and 10% on US\$75 billion worth of goods.
28	On August 28, 2019, USTR announced an increase in the tariff rate on Chinese goods worth US\$300 billion from the original 10% to 15%, and implemented it in two batches, with implementation dates of September 1 and December 15 respectively; At the same time, public opinion was sought to raise the tariff rate of \$250 billion from 25% to 30%, which took effect on October 1, 2019.
29	On September 12, 2019, President Trump announced a delay in raising tariffs on \$250 billion worth of Chinese goods imported into the United States from October 1 to October 15.
30	On September 28, 2019, Bloomberg reported that the United States was considering restricting investment portfolio flows to China.
31	On October 8, 2019, the U.S. Department of Commerce added 28 Chinese entities to the Entity Control List, including 20 government agencies (the Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region Public Security Department and Xinjiang Production and Construction Corps Public Security Bureau, etc.) and 8 enterprises (Hikvision, Dahua and iFLYTEK, etc.), and prohibited these entities from purchasing U.S. products.
32	On October 10-11, 2019, the first phase of the 13th round of China-US high-level economic and trade consultations was preliminarily reached.
33	On November 19, 2019, the U.S. Senate passed the Hong Kong Human Rights and Democracy Act, which was opposed and condemned by the Chinese central government and relevant departments in Hong Kong.
34	On December 2, 2019, the Chinese government decided to suspend the approval of applications for US military ships to undergo repairs in Hong Kong, while imposing sanctions on non-governmental organizations such as the National Democratic Foundation of the United States that have performed poorly in the Hong Kong amendment scandal.
35	On December 3, 2019, the U.S. House of Representatives passed the Uyghur Human Rights Policy Act of 2019.
36	On December 13, 2019, China and the United States reached an agreement on the text of the first phase of the economic and trade agreement. On January 15, 2020, Vice Premier Liu He and President Trump signed an agreement in the United States.
37	On January 13, 2020, the U.S. Treasury Department released its semi-annual exchange rate policy report, cancelling recognition of China as a "currency manipulator".

38 ⁹	<p>On January 15, 2020, China and the United States signed the first phase of the economic and trade agreement at the White House. The agreement is divided into eight chapters: intellectual property rights, technology transfer, trade in food and agricultural products, financial services, macroeconomic policies and exchange rates, trade expansion, bilateral assessment and dispute resolution, and final clauses. After the deal is signed, President Trump will travel to Beijing to begin the second phase of negotiations.</p>
	<p>The U.S. Trade Representative's Office released the contents of the agreement, some of which are as follows:</p>
	<p>1. In terms of tariffs, the United States maintains its previous commitment to cancel the additional tariffs imposed on the remaining \$160 billion of goods on December 15, 2019. At the same time, the tariff rate on goods already added in September (approximately \$120 billion) has been reduced from 15% to 7.5%, but the 25% additional tariff on \$250 billion of goods will continue to be maintained. President Trump said retaining some tariffs is good for the second phase of negotiations.</p>
	<p>3. With regard to technology transfer, foreign investment in the acquisition of foreign technology is prohibited.</p>
	<p>4. In terms of agriculture, China will purchase at least \$40 billion in U.S. food, agricultural products, and seafood annually for the next two years, and China should strive to increase imports by an additional \$5 billion annually. Expand the variety range of imported pork and beef, partially lift the ban on importing U.S. poultry into China, and improve the management of tariff quotas on wheat, corn, and rice.</p>
	<p>7. In terms of expanding trade, China has pledged to increase the total amount of goods and services imported from the United States by no less than \$200 billion over the next two years (based on the total amount of goods and services imported in 2017). Including four major product categories: first, manufactured goods, including industrial machinery, electrical equipment, automobiles, and steel, with an import value of at least \$120 billion in 2020 and at least \$131.9 billion in 2021. Secondly, agricultural imports will reach at least \$80 billion over the next two years. Third, energy products, with an import value of at least \$30.1 billion in 2020 and at least \$45.5 billion in 2021. Fourth, the service industry, with an import value of at least \$999 billion in 2020 and at least \$112.2 billion in 2021.</p>
39	<p>On July 6, 2022, ¹⁰ Bloomberg quoted sources familiar with the matter as saying that US officials are lobbying the Dutch authorities to further expand the ban on the export of previous generation deep ultraviolet lithography machines (DUVs) on the basis of banning the sale of state-of-the-art extreme ultraviolet lithography machines (EUVs) to China. Due to the inability to obtain export licences from the Dutch government, ASML is no longer able to export its state-of-the-art EUV lithography machines to China, priced at approximately €160 million per unit. The report states that these old DUV lithography machines targeted by the United States are one generation</p>

	<p>behind advanced technology, but they are still the most commonly used equipment for manufacturing certain non-advanced chips required for cars, mobile phones, computers, and even robots, and are still essential in the manufacture of many chips that are currently in serious shortage.</p> <p>A person familiar with the matter who did not want to be identified said Don Graves, deputy secretary of the U.S. Department of Commerce, made the request when discussing supply chain issues during his visit to the Netherlands and Belgium from the end of May to early June. During this time Don Graves also visited ASML's headquarters in Feldhofen, the Netherlands and met with the company's CEO Peter Wenninger.</p> <p>The focus of the United States is to ban the sale of the most advanced DUV model in China - the Immersion Type DUV Lithography Machine (ArFi). The person familiar with the situation also revealed that the United States is also working to pressure Japan to stop supplying the same technology to Chinese chip manufacturers, and Nikon also produces lithography machines, which are ASML's competitors in this field.</p> <p>The US' repeated coercion is aimed at thwarting China's plan to become a global leader in chip production. Bloomberg reported that if the Dutch government agrees to Washington's proposal, the scope and categories of chip manufacturing equipment currently banned from being shipped to China will be significantly expanded, which could hit Chinese chip makers hard.</p> <p>Following Bloomberg report , ASML's U.S. Depositary Receipts (ADR) fell as much as 8.3%, the largest intraday decline since March 2020. Bloomberg analysts say that if ASML is prohibited from exporting DUVs to China, its revenue may shrink by 5-10%. Shares of SMIC International and Huahong Semiconductor in Hong Kong also fell sharply on Wednesday.</p>
40	<p>On August 14, 2022, ¹¹ the U.S. Department of Commerce's Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) announced that diamond and gallium oxide (Ga₂O₃), two ultra wide bandgap semiconductor substrate materials, advanced chip EDA software tools for designing GAAFET architecture (full gate field effect transistors), and pressure gain combustion technologies for gas turbine engines will be included in the commercial control list from August 15 to control the export of these technologies.</p>
41	<p>On October 7, 2022, ¹² the U.S. Department of Commerce's Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) announced the "New Export Control on Advanced Computing and Semiconductor Manufacturing Items Exported to China", which is another escalation of U.S. sanctions against China's semiconductor industry since 2018.</p> <p>In the new export control regulations, the U.S. Department of Commerce increased restrictions on the export of chips and related production tools to China on national security grounds, mainly including: (1) restricting Chinese enterprises from obtaining high-performance chips and advanced computers; (2) restricting U.S. support for specific semiconductor activities involving China; (3) restricting China's access to advanced semiconductor</p>

	manufacturing items and equipment; and (4) adding 31 new Chinese physical companies and research institutions to the UVL (Unverified List) list.
42	<p>In November 2022, Dutch Foreign Trade Minister Schreinemacher said that "the Netherlands will not blindly copy the measures taken by the United States (for exports to China).¹³</p> <p>On December 13, 2022,¹⁴ ASML CEO Peter Wennink questioned the significance of the United States pushing the Netherlands to restrict exports to China through new rules in an interview with the newspaper NRC Handelsblad. Peter Wennink said, "Perhaps they think we should negotiate, but ASML has made sacrifices.</p> <p>He said that under the constant pressure of the United States, since 2019, the Dutch government has begun to restrict ASML from exporting the most advanced EUV Stepper to Chinese Mainland, which makes American companies selling related alternative technologies profit from it. Wennink stated that although ASML has 15% of its sales in China, the proportion of American chip equipment suppliers is "25%, sometimes even exceeding 30%". It can be seen that Wennink has discovered the beauty of a series of actions by the United States, that is, everything serves its own interests, which is vastly different from the "security of allies" it talks about.</p> <p>Subsequently, a spokesperson for ASML confirmed that Peter Wennink's remarks in the interview were accurate, but declined to comment further.</p>
43	<p>On January 28, 2023,¹⁵ after several months of negotiations, the United States, the Netherlands, and Japan finally reached a consensus on jointly restricting the export of semiconductor equipment to China. They will work together to prevent China from obtaining the technologies needed to develop advanced chips, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, and so on.</p> <p>Semiconductor equipment giants such as ASML in the Netherlands, Nikon in Japan, and TEL in Japan will all implement new standards for their exports to China. On the basis of continuing to ban the sale of EUV lithography machines to Chinese enterprises, the new alliance has expanded its regulatory scope – technology and equipment required for China's development of advanced semiconductors will be added to the ban list, including DUV immersion lithography machines.</p> <p>Has the United States reached the "strongest" agreement on restrictions on China with the Netherlands and Japan? Will force China to independently develop semiconductor equipment.</p>

Table 14. U.S. political parties and government behavioural economy in trade frictions between the U.S.-multiple countries from 2018 to 2019.

No.	Contents
1	Trade frictions between the United States and the European Union continue. ⁹ In March 2018, the United States announced that it would impose tariffs of 25% and 10% on imported steel and aluminum products, respectively,

	involving multiple economies such as the European Union, Canada, Mexico, and Japan. In response, the European Union announced that it would impose a 25% tariff on about \$3.5 billion in U.S. goods. President Trump threatened to impose a 20% tariff on cars and parts imported from the European Union.
2	In July 2018, European Commission President Juncker visited the United States, and the United States and Europe issued a joint statement agreeing to reduce trade barriers and ease trade frictions through negotiations, thus easing trade frictions between the United States and Europe. ⁹
3	In July 2019, the USTR released a list of EU goods with a proposed tariff of \$4 billion , sparking trade frictions between the United States and Europe. ⁹
4	In October 2019, the WTO ruled that the European Union and some member states illegally subsidized Airbus, and the United States had the right to impose tariffs on the EU. The US side decided to impose an additional 10% tariff on large EU civil aircraft and a 25% tariff on agricultural and other products. The European Union has said it will retaliate against the United States for illegally subsidizing Boeing. In December, Letterschitz proposed imposing 100% tariffs on \$2.4 billion worth of imported products from France, including cheese, lipstick and sparkling wine, in retaliation for France's tax on US tech giants such as Google, Amazon and Facebook. ⁹
5	Trump has repeatedly criticized unfair trade between the United States and Japan, and has "fired shots" at Japan's agricultural and auto industries. ⁹ In July 2018, U.S. Trade Representative Wright Heather said a trade deal with Japan must be negotiated. In September 2018, the United States and Japan launched negotiations on a trade agreement on goods, and the U.S. Secretary of Agriculture demanded that Japan open up its agricultural market. ⁹ In October 2018, President Trump announced that if Japan did not open its market, it would impose a 20% tariff on Japanese cars. The U.S. government has even used Japan's U.S. security protection as a pressure chip to criticize the unfairness of the U.S.-Japan Security Treaty. ⁹
6	The United States is trying to build a new world trading system that bypasses the WTO. In addition to negotiations between the United States, Europe and Japan, on July 17, 2018 , the European Union and Japan signed the Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) in Tokyo. If the United States, Japan, and Europe form an alliance, the WTO will exist in name only, the world will form two parallel markets, and the international economic and trade order will face reconstruction. However, the establishment of the U.S.-Japan alliance was not achieved overnight, and there are still many problems, such as the difficulty of achieving zero tariffs on agriculture and automobiles in Europe and Japan in the short term (especially French agriculture will be greatly affected). Subsequently, the US-Europe joint statement was strongly opposed by countries such as France. ⁹ On December 11, 2019, the WTO Appellate Body ceased operations due to the obstruction of member selection by the United States, leaving only one Appellate Body member, which was insufficient for the minimum number of

	effective members to operate. ⁹
7	<p>The United States has launched trade frictions with Mexico, the second largest source of its trade deficit. At the beginning of President Trump's term, he proposed renegotiating the U.S.-Canada Mexico Free Trade Agreement.⁹ On May 31, 2019, President Trump economized on diplomatic issues and weaponized tariffs. In order to restrict illegal immigration, he announced that starting June 10, he would impose a 5% tariff on all goods imported from Mexico; If the crisis is not resolved, the United States will continue to raise the tariff rate to 25% by October 1st, and Mexico will have to deploy the National Guard to strengthen border enforcement and accept illegal immigrants to be returned to Mexico.</p> <p>On December 10, 2019, senior officials from Canada, Mexico, and the United States signed the latest revised version of the U.S.-Mexico-Canada trade agreement. Intended to improve the enforcement of labour rights and lower the prices of biopharmaceuticals by eliminating patent clauses.</p>
8	<p>In addition, the United States has also initiated trade frictions with economies such as India, Brazil, and Argentina.⁹ On June 5, 2019, the United States terminated India's trade status under the Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) and cancelled tariff reductions for India. India immediately imposed retaliatory tariffs on 28 U.S. products such as apples and almonds.</p> <p>On December 2, 2019, President Trump announced that he would resume tariffs on steel and aluminum products from Brazil and Argentina, mainly because President Trump believed Brazil and Argentina were profiting from currency depreciation, which was unfair to American farmers.</p>

Table 15. Some economic behaviors of Political parties in the U.S. and governments involves more than 100 billion dollars in 2017-2022

No.	Contents
1	<p>On December 22, 2017, U.S. President Trump signed a \$1.5 trillion tax cut bill into law.¹⁶</p> <p>Several U.S. companies have distributed red envelopes of money to employees in celebration of tax reform. AT&T announced a \$1,000 per employee bonus for more than 200,000 employees and an additional \$1 billion investment in the United States.¹⁷</p> <p>Technology enterprises: Technology companies will benefit from the repatriation of funds. Goldman Sachs Group estimates that the current profits of U.S. companies staying overseas are as high as \$3.1 trillion. The remittance clause may result in a large tax receipt in the short term.¹⁸</p> <p>Industrial enterprises: According to Jefferies LLC, in the machinery industry, the truck industry may benefit the most. Lower corporate tax rates will give U.S. transportation companies of all sizes more money to upgrade their fleets with energy-efficient vehicles. The increase in capital expenditure deductions under the new tax law will give transportation companies another incentive</p>

	<p>to buy new cars.</p> <p>Asset Management Company: Analysts expect that most of the tax savings from this tax reform will be used to increase dividends and share buybacks. This will drive the U.S. stock market higher and increase the value of investment held by asset managers. Lower taxes for individuals, especially wealthy individuals, will also lead to more demand for financial services from asset management companies.</p> <p>Pharmaceutical companies: U.S. pharmaceutical companies will be one of the biggest beneficiaries of the profit repatriation clause in the tax reform. They have billions of dollars of profits overseas, and now they can take that cash home at a lower tax rate.</p>
2	<p>On March 23, 2018, U.S. President Trump announced that he had signed a \$1.3 trillion government funding bill.¹⁹</p>
3	<p>On the afternoon of March 27, 2020, US President Trump officially signed the \$2 trillion economic stimulus bill passed by Congress, which also means that the bill officially came into effect and became law.²⁰</p> <p>The bill was passed by the House of Representatives on the same day and submitted to President Trump. The largest stimulus bill in U.S. history includes stronger unemployment protection, corporate loan subsidies, and more medical resources for hospitals, state governments, and municipalities.</p> <p>Trump tweeted: "This is the largest stimulus package in U.S. history, twice the size of any bailout bill ever enacted.</p>
4	<p>On December 27, 2020, U.S. President Trump signed a spending package of about \$2.3 trillion, equivalent to about 10% of the U.S. gross domestic product (GDP), at Sealake Estate in Florida. To prevent the U.S. government from suspending operations on the 29th.²¹</p> <p>This spending package includes the COVID-19 economic rescue bill with a total amount of about \$900 billion and the 2021 budget bill (starting October 1 this year) with a total amount of \$1.4 trillion.</p>
5	<p>On November 15, 2021, U.S. President Joe Biden signed a bipartisan infrastructure investment bill worth about \$1 trillion into law at the White House. Economists believe the bill is insufficient to fill the huge infrastructure financing gap in the United States and has limited impact on economic growth. Biden said at the signing ceremony that the bill will make the largest investment in infrastructure such as roads, bridges, railways, and public transportation in the United States in decades, create many jobs, and ease supply chain bottlenecks.²²</p> <p>The bill includes funding for existing federal public works projects and an additional \$550 billion in infrastructure investment over five years. Compared to Biden's initial infrastructure plan of about \$2.25 trillion, the bill's investment scale has significantly decreased.</p>
6	<p>On August 9, 2022, Biden formally signed the Chip and Science Act of 2022. The 1054-page chip bill was hailed by the New York Times as the "most significant U.S. government intervention in industrial policy in decades".²³</p>

	<p>In fact, the bill is widely regarded as targeting the Chinese chip industry because of its exclusive industry support policies that prevent international semiconductor companies from continuing to invest in China. Experts point out that in the short term, the global chip industry chain will inevitably face a new round of interference.</p> <p>The total amount of the chip bill signed by the United States this time is 280 billion US dollars. The main content includes increasing investment of \$200 billion for scientific research, especially in fields such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and quantum computing, while proposing to provide \$52 billion in subsidies and additional tax credits for companies manufacturing chips in the United States.</p> <p>The bill places greater emphasis on promoting technological innovation through various measures to enhance the competitiveness of the United States itself. To achieve this goal, the U.S. federal government will spend about \$170 billion, or more than 60 percent, on the bill's science and technology innovation component over the next five years, mainly for the National Science Foundation (NSF, \$81 billion), the Department of Commerce (\$11 billion), the Department of Energy's national laboratories (\$67.9 billion), and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (\$10 billion). Government R&D investment has a leverage effect on enterprises and the market, ultimately driving an increase in overall R&D investment in society. It can be foreseen that the increase in R&D investment by the US government in the next five years is expected to drive a significant increase in corporate R&D investment.</p> <p>The bill also stipulates that chip companies that receive federal funding subsidies will not expand their advanced chip manufacturing in countries including China and Russia within the next 10 years (where advanced chips are interpreted as chips smaller than 28 nanometers). This means that from the effective date of the bill, subsidized chip companies will not be able to continue to increase production of advanced process chips in China. According to Bloomberg, both Samsung and TSMC currently have chip factories in the U.S. and China, with TSMC producing 28nm and 16nm chips in China.</p> <p>At the same time, the bill also mentions that the 28 nanometer standard will be reassessed with technological progress and may be extended to areas below 28 nanometers in the future, indicating that there may be more and more restrictions on chip companies' investment in China in the United States in the future.</p> <p>The market believes that the real purpose of the United States is actually to "pull" chip companies that could have made industrial investments in other countries back into the United States through an exclusive "rule game".</p>
7	<p>On August 16, 2022, U.S. President Joe Biden signed the \$750 billion Inflation Reduction Act of 2022, which officially took effect. Legislation includes addressing climate change and expanding health care coverage.²⁴</p> <p>The White House said, "This historic legislation will reduce energy, prescription</p>

	<p>drugs, and other health care costs for American households, address the climate crisis, reduce deficits, and allow large corporations to pay their fair share of taxes.</p> <p>The legislation allocates \$369 billion for energy security and climate investment, aiming to reduce carbon emissions by 40% by 2030. The legislation also allocated \$64 billion for subsidies under the Affordable Care Act. At the same time, the legislation allocates \$80 billion to strengthen the enforcement efforts of the U.S. Internal Revenue Service and ensure that high-income individuals and businesses do not evade taxes. In addition, the legislation also includes a 1% excise tax on stock repurchases.</p> <p>Biden called the bill "one of the most important bills in American history". However, many American media and experts believe that the bill does not solve the problem of inflation, but rather exacerbates it or further recession the U.S. economy, putting the country in a difficult position. Some American media have even compared the bill to another "poison" the Biden administration has prescribed for the U.S. economy.</p>
8	<p>On December 29, 2022, the United States President Joe Biden signed a about \$1.7 trillion federal spending bill that will provide funds for the functioning of the U.S. federal government, and will also include tens of billions of dollars in aid to Ukraine.²⁵</p> <p>According to the Associated Press, the Democratic-controlled House of Representatives passed a \$1.7 trillion spending bill on December 22 local time with 225 votes in favor and 201 votes against. Biden must sign the bill by the evening of the 30th to avoid a shutdown of U.S. government departments. Biden signed the bill while on vacation in the U.S. Virgin Islands.</p>

Table 16. Records of US political parties and governments suppressing and intervening in the operation of Huawei, a privately owned company owned by employees, between 2018 and 2021.²⁶⁻²⁹

No.	Contents
	2018
1	On January 9, 2018, Huawei lost its phone order to AT&T.
2	On February 13, 2018, FBI Director Chris Wray warned against buying Huawei phones.
3	On March 22, 2018, Huawei Mobile lost support from Best Buy.
4	On May 2, 2018, the U.S. Department of Defense banned the sale of Huawei and ZTE smartphones on U.S. military bases.
5	On June 7, 2018, the U.S. Congress called on Google to stop cooperating with Huawei.
6	On 11 July 2018, Australia banned Huawei from participating in the construction of 5G networks.
7	On December 5, 2018, British operator BT Sheng announced that it would eliminate Huawei's 4G equipment and not purchase Huawei's 5G core network equipment.

8	On December 7, 2018, Reuters reported that Japan would stop purchasing equipment from Huawei and ZTE.
9	On December 12, 2018, the Canadian court granted Meng Wanzhou \$10 million in bail.
	2019
10	On January 3, 2019, a report suggested that President Trump would use executive orders to ban sales by Huawei and ZTE.
11	On January 4, 2019, senators proposed a bipartisan bill to address concerns about Huawei.
12	On January 23, 2019, the media reported that Meng Wanzhou could be extradited to the United States.
13	On January 29, 2019, the United States filed 23 lawsuits against Huawei on suspicion of stealing trade secrets and fraud.
14	On February 4, 2019, the U.S. FBI raided Huawei's laboratory. In addition, two Huawei employees were expelled from Denmark after checking their work permits.
15	On February 6, 2019, the U.S. government urged European countries not to purchase Huawei's 5G equipment.
16	On February 21, 2019, U.S. Secretary of State Peng Peiao said that countries using Huawei technology pose a risk to the United States.
17	On February 22, 2019, it was reported that Italian politicians were pushing for a Huawei 5G ban.
18	On March 1, 2019, Meng Wanzhou's extradition hearing was approved in Canada, and the United States warned the Philippines not to use Huawei 5G devices.
19	On March 8, 2019, Huawei sued the U.S. government for a ban on its equipment.
20	On March 12, 2019, the United States warned Germany that Huawei must be banned, otherwise it would restrict intelligence sharing with Germany.
21	On March 28, 2019, UK regulators warned that Huawei's products "significantly increased risks."
22	On April 21, 2019, the Central Intelligence Agency said Huawei was funded by China's national security department.
23	On May 2, 2019, the leak of information about Huawei led to the dismissal of British Defence Secretary Gavin Williamson.
24	On May 15, 2019, President Trump effectively banned Huawei through a national security order.
25	On May 19, 2019, Google removed Huawei phones from the Android upgrade list.
26	On May 20, 2019, Huawei received a temporary reprieve from the US trade ban, prompting Google to temporarily resume work.
27	On May 22, 2019, chip design company Arm abandoned Huawei, while Mate 20 X canceled its launch in the UK.

28	On May 23, 2019, it was reported that the United States accused Huawei of lying in China's relations.
29	On May 30, 2019, the SD Association and Wi-Fi Alliance restored Huawei's membership.
30	On June 3, 2019, the academic organization IEEE lifted a week-long ban on Huawei scientists from reviewing technical papers.
31	On June 7, 2019, Facebook stopped allowing Huawei to pre-install its apps. It was reported that Google had warned President Trump administration that its Huawei ban would pose a national security risk.
32	On June 24, 2019, the FCC commissioner hoped Huawei would detach from the U.S. network, and the President Trump government is considering requiring the manufacture of 5G devices outside China.
33	On June 25, 2019, it was reported that a U.S. company bypassed Trump's ban on selling products to Huawei, while FedEx sued the Department of Commerce for transferring Huawei packages.
34	On July 1, 2019, President Trump government officials said easing restrictions on Huawei would only apply to products widely available on the market.
35	On July 16, 2019, a bipartisan group of U.S. senators introduced 5G legislation that would blacklist Huawei.
36	On July 25, 2019, it was reported that after the implementation of the ban in the United States, the OEM company Weichuangli "confiscated" Huawei products worth \$100 million.
37	On August 7, 2019, the Trump administration announced that it would prohibit the government from doing business with Huawei, and Republican senators would target Google Huawei project.
38	On August 19, 2019, the U.S. Department of Commerce extended the probation period, allowing U.S. companies to cooperate with Huawei.
39	On September 3, 2019, Huawei accused the United States of using cyberattacks and threats to disrupt its business.
40	On September 9, 2019, Microsoft President Brad Smith requested more evidence from the U.S. government to support his Huawei ban. U.S. prosecutors have accused a Chinese professor with fraud for allegedly purchasing technology from a California company for Huawei's benefit.
41	On October 28, 2019, the FCC announced that it would cut off financial support for wireless carriers using Huawei and ZTE devices.
42	On November 8, 2019, Trump's technology chief criticized countries for "opening their arms" to China.
43	On November 22, 2019, the FCC banned Huawei and ZTE from receiving federal subsidies, while senators hoped President Trump would stop allowing U.S. companies to sell licenses to Huawei.
44	On December 17, 2019, Huawei will launch the P40 Pro without Google services in March 2020. Telecom Spain has announced that it will significantly reduce the use of Huawei's core 5G network equipment.
	2020

45	On January 9, 2020, Senator Tom Cotton announced a bill prohibiting the United States from sharing intelligence with countries using Huawei 5G technology.
46	On January 14, 2020, the United States urged British officials to prevent Huawei from entering its 5G network. U.S. senators have proposed more than \$1 billion in 5G subsidies to offset Huawei's dominance.
47	On January 30, 2020, Australian politicians rejected a proposal to reopen the Huawei 5G ban.
48	On February 7, 2020, U.S. Attorney General William Barr suggested that the United States has a "controlling interest" in Ericsson or Nokia to deal with Huawei.
49	On February 13, 2020, the U.S. Department of Justice accused Huawei of extortion and theft of trade secrets.
50	<p>On May 15, 2020, the U.S. Department of Commerce's Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) officially sent two consecutive messages about Huawei:</p> <p>One is to announce a 90-day extension of the existing Temporary General License (TGL) authorization period for Huawei Technology Co., Ltd. and its non-U.S. branches on the Entity List.</p> <p>The second is to strictly restrict Huawei's use of American technology, software design, and semiconductor chip manufacturing.</p> <p>On May 15, 2020, the United States upgraded the ban. The U.S. Department of Commerce said it was developing a more "comprehensive plan." Not only U.S. companies, but also companies around the world, must obtain U.S. approval as long as they use U.S. equipment and technology (up to a certain proportion) to produce chips for Huawei.</p> <p>The aim of the ban is to sever Huawei's ties with chip makers such as TSMC and SMIC. Originally, Huawei had not invested in chip manufacturing before, and chips designed by Huawei HiSilicon needed to be produced in other chip manufacturing plants. TSMC has announced that it will cut off Huawei's power supply after September 14. This decision directly blocked Huawei's supply of high-end mobile phone chips. And this fall, Huawei's flagship Mate 40 phone will be released, equipped with the new Kirin 9000 chip, which will become out of print.</p> <p>In order to "survive", Huawei re-planned its supply chain in June and purchased a large number of chips from MediaTek, a mobile phone chip supplier in Taiwan.</p>
51	On August 17, 2020, the U.S. Department of Commerce's Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) issued a revised ban on Huawei, which further restricted Huawei's products produced using U.S. technology and software, and added 38 Huawei subsidiaries to the entity list.
52	September 15, 2020 was an unusual day, marking the official entry into force of the US government's chip sanctions against Huawei. ²⁷
	2021
53	On March 12, 2021, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC)

	<p>Department of Public Safety and the Department of Homeland Security (HHS) included five Chinese companies, including Huawei, in the list of untrusted suppliers because they believed the telecommunications equipment and services produced by these companies would pose "unacceptable risks" to the national security and citizen security of the United States. Some of the communications products and services produced by the aforementioned companies will be dismantled within the United States.²⁸</p> <p>According to the Federal Communications Commission's notice on March 12, Huawei and ZTE, which are the most widely restricted, are restricted from "the telecommunications equipment they produce or provide, including telecommunications or video surveillance services they produce or provide, or use".</p>
54	<p>Biden signs the Secure Equipment Act of 2021²⁹</p> <p>According to Reuters, on Thursday (November 11, 2021) local time, US President Biden signed the latest bill: the Secure Equipment Act of 2021. Require the Federal Communications Commission to adopt rules that explicitly prohibit the review or approval of any device authorization applications that pose an unacceptable risk to national security.</p> <p>This is an additional ban on Huawei, ZTE, Haikang, and others.</p> <p>However, it is currently unknown whether it will involve suppliers such as SMIC International. In a broad sense, any company associated with it may be affected. Especially for nodes where Chinese semiconductors expand production. If EUV does not provide it, and DUV does not provide it, Chinese semiconductors may encounter a black swan.</p>

China's annual chip demand is \$300 billion. Prior to 2018, due to China's adherence to the principle of globalization proposed by the United States, China's self-sufficiency rate was only 5%, with the United States and its allies reaping huge benefits. However, since the US trade embargo in 2020, China's self-sufficiency rate has increased to about 10%,³⁰ resulting in a loss of about \$15 billion for the US market. By 2022, China's self-sufficiency in chips will increase to about 16-17%, resulting in the loss of another \$15 billion market for the US and its allies. 2023 will be a turning point year. After four years of construction from 2020 to 2023, China's chip production lines will surpass 300, forming a powerful production capacity. It is estimated that China's self-sufficiency rate in chips will approach 25% by 2023, with the most conservative estimate predicting that China's chip self-sufficiency rate will reach 50% by 2025. This means that the US and its allies will lose a market worth \$150 billion to \$200 billion in China.

According to customs data, from January to April this year, China significantly reduced chip imports, with a cumulative order reduction amount of up to CNY 250 billion. The number of imported chips from January to March was 108.2 billion, a year-on-year decrease of 32.1 billion. In April, the number of imported chips was 38.72 billion, down 0.2% year-on-year. If we add it all up, the number of chips imported by China from January to April was 146.84 billion, a decrease of 21.1% year-on-year, and

a decrease of 39.3 billion compared to the same period last year. If we split it evenly, it would be a decrease of 328 million chips in one day.³¹

Restricted by the actions of political parties in the United States and the government, TSMC, the world's leading chip manufacturer, fell its sales performance by nearly 15% in April this year,³¹ and chip manufacturers in the United States, Japan and South Korea have begun to significantly reduce chip prices. Korean media reported that Samsung's chip inventory has more than tripled, with a value of CNY 340 billion in inventory. The high inventory has already overwhelmed Samsung. Samsung is selling chips at a reduced price in China, the world's largest chip market, hoping to seize the market and clear inventory by taking advantage of Meguiar's safety review by China. However, the United States requires Samsung not to expand chip sales in the Chinese market.³² Faced with such a dilemma, the United States suddenly took action against Samsung, accusing it of infringing the patents of a US company and imposing a fine of 400 billion Korean won on Samsung, which is equivalent to stealing two-thirds of Samsung's profits. This is definitely a disaster for Samsung and will cause the company's financial chain to become tense.³²

According to the financial report, Intel's revenue for the first quarter of 2023 was \$11.7 billion, a year-on-year decrease of 36%, and a net profit loss of \$2.76 billion, marking the second consecutive quarterly loss.³³

From the behavioral analysis above, which country can replicate the behavior of the United States in recent years, in order to protect or obtain significant economic benefits? Is the American economic model a free and democratic market economy? Can the American political, economic, and democratic model be fully replicated? The answer is clearly no.

The above economic and management behaviors have shown the economic and management behaviors of politicians, government and political parties. There are also more examples of U.S. government intervention in economic operations. From a historical perspective on the American economic system, does this fact not precisely indicate that politician or statesman behavior economy, government behavior economy and political party behavior economy have a large degree and component in the American economic system? The claim that the United States is a completely market-oriented economy is incorrect and a false impression. Economists ignore historical facts and lack a historical, philosophical, and logical perspective.

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